

Efficient Monitoring of Library Call Invocation

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Abstract—The ability to monitor when user code invokes a library function offers numerous advantages. For example, during black-box testing of code, high-level control-flow integrity (CFI) checking, run-time access-control policy enforcement and so on. However, for this technique to be useful it must be efficient and able to function even when the target application is provided only as a statically linked executable. In an earlier paper we demonstrated how library calls may be intercepted using wrappers. But this approach works only with dynamically linked code and requires labour-intensive processing of the function arguments. Under the current scheme, each library constitutes a separate code-region. At any point in time, only pages belonging to that one region are marked as executable, so when code branches to a page outside the ‘home’ region, it will land in a non-executable page, a fault will occur and the kernel will take over. By adding suitable code to the kernel, we can determine (a) whether the call should go ahead, (b) whether the arguments are acceptable and (c) ensure that the kernel will be informed when the code returns from the called function. In this paper we present our technique by analyzing the interception of a known exploit of the NGINX server. We show that our mechanism can detect and contain the attack and discuss the performance overheads of our mechanism.

Index Terms—Monitoring, Library calls, Invocation, Library containers

I. INTRODUCTION

As the advancement of technology offers capabilities which result in attackers on every level getting more competent and effective, attacks have become more elaborate. Therefore, we need to establish an adequate level of security in software systems. Complete security of a program is unfeasible and so it becomes imperative to detect a situation where a program enters a possibly insecure state and take some action to respond to it. Our idea is to implement such actions at an abstract level, between the Operating System (OS) and a running application.

Mechanisms such as CFI [1], `systrace(8)` [2], SecModule [3], etc., aim to control the behavior of a program based on some predetermined policy. When the program attempts to perform some action that is in conflict with its execution policy, the security mechanism detects this and takes corrective action. Unlike most runtime security mechanisms, where violations in most cases lead to the termination of the offending process, the call intercept technique offers a variety of options in dealing with the security breach. For example, `systrace(8)` may rewrite function arguments (e.g. truncate or replace strings), or return an error without making the call.

A key concern is the level at which the call intercept should be made. Some papers propose to carry out the checks at the

machine language level, via call graphs, while others at the system call level. We believe that carrying out the analysis at an even higher level has many benefits, not least being close to the application logic. With this in mind, we chose to base our system on the monitoring of library calls. We, therefore, had to consider the performance penalty of carrying out our high-level monitoring.

Our compromise was to designate the main application and each library as separate areas and monitor program jumps from one area to another. We then program the Memory Management Unit (MMU) in such a way so as to cause a fault when control flow moves from one area to another. We do this by designating all code pages outside the currently executing area, as non-executable. In this way, a jump within the current area will be carried out normally, but a jump to a page belonging to another area will cause a fault. Our technique is very efficient, while at the same time allowing `systrace`-like control of function invocation, argument checking and modification etc.

The remainder of this paper is organized in the following manner: Section II describes related work done to address relevant issues. In Section III we detail the design of our approach. In Section IV, we describe the implementation details. In Section V, we present a simple use-case scenario to test our mechanism, including the performance evaluation from using our custom kernel. Section VI concludes this work.

II. RELATED WORK

This work is relevant to our earlier work on Access Controls For Libraries and Modules (SecModule) [3]. This framework forces user-level code to perform library calls only via a library policy enforcement engine providing mandatory policy checks over not just system calls, as in the case of `systrace(8)` [2], but calls to user-level libraries as well. The access rights in question would be whether a process (which may be malicious) is allowed to execute some function held securely in a library module. This framework retrofits functions in order to be included in a secure “enclosure” (SecModule). The kernel has a list of all the SecModules and when a process asks for access to a secured function, the kernel verifies that the requested SecModule is registered and that the process is valid with respect to its policy. Then, it allows that and only that process to use only the specific function. This means that access to a specific function or procedure is controlled by the kernel. While this is particularly suited to SecModule-enabled applications, the overhead of two context switches per function

invocation (once to transfer control to the kernel and – when it reaches a decision – once more to transfer control back to the caller), makes the technique quite expensive for more general use. One of the issues identified by the authors of the SecModule paper is the difficulty in encapsulating library modules. This manual process is error prone and extremely labor intensive, since most of the applications compiled within the framework required patching. Another issue is the inability to evaluate call arguments. Although they are contained in a known structure pointed to by a stack pointer, their examination requires lots of casting in the C++ functions, which in turn needs additional information for these functions held in the module.

Also relevant to our work is the `systrace(8)` [2] system which supports fine-grained policy generation. It guards the calls to the operating system at the lowest level, enforcing policies that restrict the actions an attacker can take to compromise a system. In the process, however, it makes higher-level actions indistinguishable. A high-level intent would be lost in a multitude of low-level calls. For example, consider the `mktemp(3)` function, that generates a unique temporary file name. Programs that use this function can create and use temporary files. To achieve this, `mktemp(3)` first checks if a file name already exists. If not, then it creates and opens the file with the specific name. During this sequence of events, several system calls (`stat(2)`, `open(2)`, `mkdir(2)`, etc) are being made. To prevent arbitrary usage of these functions (e.g., during a race between testing whether the name exists and opening the file, when an attacker can create a symbolic link to an inaccessible file and have access to it from a privileged program), the system calls would need to be examined and policies enforced under a finer-grained framework, like `systrace(8)`). However, this kind of framework would need to check these calls that result in a number of lower-level calls to the operating system. Since only the high-level calls are of importance in this case, the examination of underlying calls would be not only unnecessary, but undesired too. The fine-grain control offered by the framework, while checking calls required by system or user level libraries when implementing complex operations, is overly verbose. Additionally, it may leave a library in an inconsistent state if the sequence of these calls is interrupted in the middle of execution by a misconfiguration [3]. Furthermore, for applications that use high-level abstractions away from low-level system calls, there may be difficulties generating precise policies. Later research [4] showed that concurrency vulnerabilities were discovered, that gave an attacker the ability to construct a race between the engine and a malicious processes to bypass protections. More specifically, in a multiprocessor environment, the arguments of a system call were stored by a process in shared memory. After `systrace(8)` performed the check and permitted the call, another malicious process had a time window to replace the cleared arguments in shared memory, effectively negating the presence of `systrace(8)` and evading its restrictions. In a uniprocessor environment, this could be achieved by forcing a page fault or in-kernel blocking, so the kernel would yield

to the attacking user process.

Multics [5] operating system uses multiple rings of protection [5]–[8] that isolate the most-privileged code from other processes, forming a hierarchical layering. Each process is associated with multiple rings – domains – so it is necessary to change the domain of execution of a process. This way the process can access specific domains only when particular programs are executed. To prevent arbitrary usage, specific “gates” between rings are provided to allow passing from an outer (less-privileged) to an inner (more-privileged) ring, restricting access to resources of one layer from programs of another layer. The change of domain occurs only after the control is transferred to a gate of another domain. Switching to a lower ring requires more access rights as opposed to a higher ring where reduced rights suffice. Downward switching requires a control transfer to a gate of an inner ring, if the transfer is to be allowed, whereas an upward domain switch is an unrestricted transfer that can be performed by any process. Nevertheless, the need-to-know principle cannot be enforced, because if a resource needs to be accessible by a ring *a* but not from another *b*, then *a* needs to be lower than *b*. But, in this case every resource in *b* is accessible from *a*.

Abadi et al. propose CFI [1] which enforces the execution of a program to adhere to a control flow graph (CFG), which is statically computed at compile time. If the flow of execution does not follow the predetermined CFG, an attack is detected. This approach, however, suffers from two main disadvantages. First, the implementation is coarse-grained. Computing a complete and accurate CFG is difficult since there are many indirect control flow transfers (jumps, returns, etc.) or libraries dynamically linked at run-time. Furthermore, the interception and checking of all the control transfers incur substantial performance overhead.

In our previous work [9], we implement access control similar to the work presented above. Under our scheme, each call to an external function of a library is intercepted and checked to ensure that it complies with the security policy associated with the running program. Every time a call to such a function is made, its arguments are examined and it is vetted by policy evaluation code to determine whether the control flow transfer is warranted. This allows high-level policy checks to be carried out in a similar fashion to the `systrace(8)` engine [2] – which, however operates at the system call level – and SecModule [3] that introduces a form of authentication when calling functions from a library. As a use-case analysis we retrofit the OpenSSL library to intercept function calls. Their arguments are checked and policy evaluation code is run, before continuing with the execution of the program. Additionally, we can use our mechanism to examine the calls inside an instrumented library and provide a trail of executed functions. Our approach is transparent to the user applications, since it can work in the background without the applications ever knowing its existence. Furthermore, there is no need to have or modify the source code of any application, making the mechanism suitable for legacy applications as well as binary programs. Since this is a user-space mechanism, there

Fig. 1. Sequence of events when setting/clearing NX-bit

is no need to invoke the kernel, meaning there are no context switches, which saves performance overhead. Additionally, it can be easily adopted in real-life environments. To demonstrate the applicability of our work, we used it to produce two internal reports, at TU Braunschweig [10], [11], where the Sophos security anti-virus product – which is offered to our academic community – was analyzed. During the update procedure, we were able to retrieve the credentials used to authenticate the client to the update server and customize several critical internal files (which we should not be able to do), using information produced by our implementation. However, our approach is not without its disadvantages. It relies on dynamic library hooking, so it is unsuitable to trace statically-linked applications. There is, also, a slight increase in code size compared to the original library version. Moreover, it can only protect programs written in C/C++ and it can be bypassed by a highly-skilled attacker who is aware of its existence and is able to manipulate the program’s memory.

III. DESIGN

Our approach aims to provide a custom Linux kernel that leverages the MMU in order to separate the memory of a process into regions, based on the dynamic libraries that are loaded upon a program’s execution. When an untrusted, user-space application issues a call to a protected function, our custom kernel intercepts it, before allowing it to continue to the intended library.

In order to intercept the library call, our system loops through all the memory regions of a running process and marks all the executable ones (e.g. *text/code* region) as non-executable (Figure 1). These regions are where the actual executable code of the program or of a shared object (external library) is found. When a program is running it issues, for example, a call to a *libm* function. After the transition, all the other executable regions have their NX-bit set. If from there the flow of execution is transferred to another library, the same procedure happens again. In a similar fashion, the regions change from executable to non-executable when the flow returns upon execution completion. This causes a page fault when the process tries to call a function in a library, since all the functions are located in the previously executable

Fig. 2. Page fault sequence

regions. The page fault handler is, then, invoked to resolve the issue. In order to continue executing, we mark the specific non-executable region as executable and continue with the function call. After it is executed normally, we may need to make the region non-executable again (see section IV) and the whole procedure starts from the beginning. Figure 2 shows this sequence of events. This way we are able to intercept all the calls inside the libraries that an application uses.

Furthermore, in order to avoid being overly verbose, we chose to monitor the execution at an abstract level. Our approach operates at the granularity of a library. For example, consider when a program calls the *printf(3)* function from *libc* library. Internally *printf(3)*, first, parses the arguments of the call, i.e. output format (how) and printable arguments (what) and then passes them as input to *vfprintf(3)*, another function of *libc*. Then, *vfprintf(3)* analyzes these inputs and displays the text in the desired format. We do not concern ourselves with how a library, internally, handles a call to one of its functions, which is left to the library designer.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

To actualize our approach, we used Linux kernel version 4.16.7. In this preliminary system we added a custom system call to jump-start our mechanism, which we issue from a user-space application. The system call goes through the list of processes that the kernel has in store, similarly to the `/proc/<pid>/maps` kernel utility. For a process or thread, it identifies the regions of contiguous virtual memory (Virtual Memory Areas - VMA) that are executable and marks them as non-executable (Figure 2 (1)). This is done by changing the flags of a specific VMA. These flags designate the access rights of a VMA (e.g., if it is read-only, writable, executable, etc.). In our case, we interested in the `VM_EXEC` flag. The modification of it can be one of two actions: (a) clear, which means the flag becomes zero “0” and execution is forbidden from the VMA and (b) set, which means `VM_EXEC` becomes one “1” and the VMA becomes executable.

After this point, when a process tries to execute a function from a dynamic library, it will land on an address in a non-executable page (Figure 2 (2)), which will result in a page fault. An error code is associated with every fault, that

Name	Value	Description
X86_PF_PROT	1 << 0	0: no page found 1: protection fault
X86_PF_WRITE	1 << 1	0: read access 1: write access
X86_PF_USER	1 << 2	0: kernel-mode access 1: user-mode access
X86_PF_RSVD	1 << 3	1: use of reserved bit detected
X86_PF_INSTR	1 << 4	1: fault was an instruction fetch
X86_PF_PK	1 << 5	1: protection keys block access

TABLE I
PAGE FAULT ERROR CODE BITS

represents what kind it is. The bits of an error code can be found in Table I [12].

In our case, the error code produced has a value of $15_{16} = 21_{10} = 010101_2$. When we correlate this number with Table I, we can see that the bits X86_PF_PROT, X86_PF_USER and X86_PF_INSTR have a value of one “1”. This means that this was a protection fault caused by a user-mode read access (X86_PF_WRITE is zero “0”) when an instruction fetch was attempted. In other words, a user-space application tried to read from a page that is protected against this action.

When a page fault occurs, the Page Fault Exception Handler [13] intervenes to handle it. This is done through the interrupt service function `do_page_fault()` (Intel IA-64 architecture). At this point and before the function has a chance to address the fault by itself, we step in and interject our custom system (Figure 2 (3)).

In order for execution to continue, we need to make the memory executable again, which we accomplish based on the virtual address of the function that caused the page fault. In memory, there is a mapping between virtual and physical addresses. Each of these translations is stored at an in-memory table called Page Table (PT). Dedicated to it is a cache of the most common Page Table Entries (PTE), the Translation Lookaside Buffer (TLB), which is used to boost performance when accessing a memory location. Every time we want to modify a PTE, we perform a page table walk (go through the multi-level PT [14] in its entirety) (Figure 3) to find the specific PTE and then clear the processor cache and the TLB from any record of it, in order the modification take effect. Both the PTE and the VMA that correspond to a specific virtual address need to be executable, if code from that address is to be executed.

In the Intel IA-64 architecture, the most significant bit of a PTE is the No-eXecute (NX) bit [15], which is used to designate a page where execution of code is not permitted. Inversely from the case of the `VM_EXEC` flag, the modification of the NX-bit can be: (a) set, which means the NX-bit becomes one “1” and execution is forbidden from the page and

Fig. 3. Page table walk

```
63|62|...|35|34|33|32|31|30|29|28|27|26|25|24|23|22|21|20|19|18|17|16|15|14|13|12|11|10|9|8|7|6|5|4|3|2|1|0
0|0|...|0|0|1|1|1|1|0|0|0|0|1|0|0|0|0|0|1|0|1|1|1|1|0|0|0|0|0|0|0|0|1|0|0|1|0|0|1|0|1
```

(a) Bit values of an executable page

```
63|62|...|35|34|33|32|31|30|29|28|27|26|25|24|23|22|21|20|19|18|17|16|15|14|13|12|11|10|9|8|7|6|5|4|3|2|1|0
1|0|...|0|0|1|1|1|1|0|0|0|0|1|0|0|0|0|0|1|0|1|1|1|1|0|0|0|0|0|0|0|0|1|0|0|1|0|1
```

(b) Bit values of a non-executable page

Fig. 4. PTE value comparison of executable and non-executable pages

(b) clear, which means the NX-bit becomes zero “0” and the page becomes executable. For example, in our implementation, when the NX-bit is clear, the value of a specific PTE that represents an executable page can be seen in Figure 4(a). After we set it, the value becomes that of Figure 4(b). Comparing the two values, we can see that the only difference is in the most significant (64th) bit which is the NX-bit. Bit numbers 36 through 61 have a zero value and have been omitted for convenience.

After clearing the NX-bit and setting the `VM_EXEC` flag, the function call continues. Following its completion, we may need to make the region non-executable again (Figure 2 (4)). In order to determine this, we implement a form of shadow stack [16]–[18]. The original idea behind shadow stacks is that when a function is called, the return address of that call is stored in a separate protected memory region - the shadow stack - where an attacker cannot have access. When the function returns, the saved return address is either compared against the program’s return address on the main stack, or it is placed directly on the main stack overwriting the return address. In our case, we leverage this to save the virtual address of the function where the page fault occurred. Before taking any further steps, we retrieve the address of the previous faulting function from the shadow stack and store there the current faulting address to retrieve at the next iteration (Figure 5 (1) and (2)).

Continuing, we mark the VMA and PTE that correspond to the current faulting address as executable (Figure 5 (3)). In order to adhere to the library-level granularity of our mechanism, we then compare the VMA to the one of the previous address and if they are not the same (meaning different executables/libraries), we mark the previous VMA and PTE as non-executable (Figure 5 (4a)). In a different case (same executable/library), we continue with the execution (Figure 5 (4b)). This means that if there is no change in the

Fig. 5. Shadow stack implementation

library, the VMA remains executable between internal library calls or different calls to the same library. However, the PTEs continue to change, but only the current one is executable. Since both the VMA and PTE need to be executable to properly execute code, we still receive a page fault for the next faulting address, even inside the same executable VMA. This way, we are able to intercept this fault also and start the procedure from the beginning to deal with the next fault.

V. USE-CASE STUDY

In this section, we present a scenario where a vulnerability of an application is exploited to affect the underlying system. In our use-case, we use a vulnerable version of NGINX HTTP server, where a buffer overflow is triggered under specific circumstances to launch a Denial-of-Service (DoS)/arbitrary code execution attack, in order to compromise the application. By using our custom kernel to observe the calls the server issues to external library functions (and the subsequent internal library calls), we can better understand the behavior of the attack and provide a signature of the way it works. Hence, we can recognize it when it happens and block it before causing any damage.

A. NGINX stack-based buffer overflow

CVE-2013-2028 [19] is a stack-based buffer overflow vulnerability related to the chunk size of an HTTP request with the header `Transfer-Encoding: chunked`. It was discovered in 2013 and received a high severity score [19]. Specifically, the `ngx_http_parse_chunked` function in `http/ngx_http_parse.c` in NGINX server versions 1.3.9 through 1.4.0 with the default setup, allows remote attackers to cause a crash via a DoS attack or execute arbitrary code when a request with a large chunk size is received, which triggers an integer signedness error and a buffer overflow.

B. Custom kernel implementation

Although the vulnerability described in the previous section was addressed in versions later than 1.4.0, we can use our prototype to examine the chain of calls that NGINX makes to its external libraries (as well as the internal library calls), which result in a crash or remote shell when the vulnerability is exploited.

There are several exploits available online [20]–[24] implementing either a DoS attack or a Code Reuse Attack (CRA) as proof-of-concept. CRAs form snippets of code, “gadgets”, chaining together legitimate commands already in a program’s memory (including its external libraries). Common forms of CRAs are Return Oriented Programming (ROP) where each gadget ends with a return instruction and Jump Oriented Programming (JOP)/Call Oriented Programming (COP) where each gadget ends with an indirect jump/call instruction. In order to prove the applicability and effectiveness of our custom kernel, we chose a ROP attack described in [23] due to the simplicity of the exploitation script and its impact in real-world applications.

```

1 [88.812529] ==[2578] start __do_page_fault 7f358be3e890===
2 [88.812531] 7f358be38000-7f358be50000 r-xp /lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/libpthread-2.23.so
3 [88.812533] NX bit before: 1, SET
4 [88.812538] NX bit after: 0, CLEAR
5 [88.812539] 7f358be38000-7f358be50000 r-xp /lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/libpthread-2.23.so
6 [88.812540] prev_addr: 7f358be3db30
7 [88.812540] ==[2578] end __do_page_fault 7f358be3e890===
8 [88.812556] ==[2578] start __do_page_fault 41d2d0===
9 [88.812558] 400000-495000 r--p /usr/local/nginx/sbin/nginx
10 [88.812560] NX bit before: 1, SET
11 [88.812560] NX bit after: 0, CLEAR
12 [88.812561] 400000-495000 r-xp /usr/local/nginx/sbin/nginx
13 [88.812562] prev_addr: 7f358be3e890
14 [88.812563] prev NX bit before: 0, CLEAR
15 [88.812567] prev NX bit after: 1, SET
16 [88.812568] ==[2578] end __do_page_fault 41d2d0===
17 [88.812579] ==[2578] start __do_page_fault 41ea5e===
18 [88.812580] 400000-495000 r-xp /usr/local/nginx/sbin/nginx
19 [88.812582] NX bit before: 1, SET
20 [88.812583] NX bit after: 0, CLEAR
21 [88.812584] 400000-495000 r-xp /usr/local/nginx/sbin/nginx
22 [88.812584] prev_addr: 41d2d0
23 [88.812585] ==[2578] end __do_page_fault 41ea5e===

```

Fig. 6. Custom kernel output after exploitation

From the excerpt of the output of our approach in Figure 6, we can see what happens when the exploit is run against the vulnerable NGINX server. We can distinguish both cases where the current executable/library is both different and the same as the previous one. For example, in lines 8-16 the flow of execution is inside the main executable. In lines 9 and 10 we can see that when the fault occurs, the VMA is non-executable ($r - p$), as well as the PTE (NX-bit 1, SET). Continuing, we mark the current PTE and VMA as executable (NX-bit 0, CLEAR and $r - xp$). Since previously (lines 1-7) the flow was inside a different library (`libpthread`), that library is now marked as non-executable. However, in the next iteration (lines 17-23), although the VMA remains the same so it is executable as before (lines 18 and 21 $r - xp$), the PTE changes (line 19), so we get a page fault which we intercept and rectify (line 20) in order to continue executing.

As the exploitation unfolds, we monitor its progress and we manage to identify a characteristic sequence of calls to executables/libraries (including the internal ones) and produce a trail of it (Table II). Consequently, the next time our mechanism recognizes the same fingerprint, it will be able to intercept and mitigate the attack.

1) 2 x libpthread	19) 1 x libnss_compat
2) 2 x nginx	20) 1 x ld
3) 5 x ld	21) 1 x libnss_compat
4) 1 x libpthread	22) 1 x libpthread
5) 1 x nginx	23) 1 x libnss_compat
6) 2 x ld	24) 1 x libpthread
7) 2 x libnss_compat	25) 2 x libnss_compat
8) 1 x libpthread	26) 2 x libpthread
9) 1 x libnss_compat	27) 1 x nginx
10) 1 x ld	28) 1 x libpthread
11) 1 x libnss_compat	29) 4 x nginx
12) 1 x ld	30) 1 x libpthread
13) 1 x libnss_compat	31) 3 x nginx
14) 1 x ld	32) 1 x libpthread
15) 1 x libnss_compat	33) 3 x nginx
16) 1 x ld	34) 1 x libpthread
17) 1 x libnss_compat	35) 1 x nginx
18) 1 x ld	36) 1 x libpthread

TABLE II
LIBRARY CALL SEQUENCE

Fig. 7. Performance evaluation of an NGINX instance using our custom kernel

C. Performance evaluation

In order to evaluate the performance overhead introduced by our mechanism, we implement a simple Python script that issues HTTP requests to a running instance of NGINX server. Our test-bed is a Virtual Machine (VM) running Ubuntu 16.04 x86_64 and Linux kernel version 4.16.7, with 8Gb of RAM and an AMD FX-8370 Eight-Core processor (six cores dedicated to the VM). The Python script sends ten sequences of requests of two thousand requests per sequence. For each request, we measure the time required to send the request, receive the response and close the connection. Then we calculate the average time of each sequence. As we can see in Figure 7, our implementation suffers only from a slight increase in average run-time overhead, ranging from 1.3% to 11.4%.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we present an extension of our previous work (LLPE) on the side of the Linux kernel, that intercepts calls to external libraries/executables, as well as internal calls within them, in an efficient manner. This way, we are able to manipulate the flow of execution, monitor access to executables/libraries and change their functionality when there is suspicion of foul play. We exploit a known NGINX vulnerability and produce a characteristic trail of calls that shows the high-level behavior of the application under attack. Our approach is transparent and can be used on binary/legacy applications and existing environments, as well as serve as a complimentary measure of defense alongside already implemented mechanisms.

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